

1 **Activation of NOD2 by the Hepatitis C virus.**

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6 Innate immune sensing of virus is incompletely understood. We used a primary hepatocyte cell culture
7 system to study HCV infection *in vitro*. We demonstrate here activation of NLR receptor *Nod2* by the
8 Hepatitis C virus.

9 Citations

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